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Diagnostic value of ^{99m}Tc -MIBI SPECT in preoperative localization for minimally invasive video assisted parathyroid surgery

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Introduction: Experienced surgeons can cure primary hyperparathyroidism with bilateral neck exploration in most patients (up to 95% of cases) without the aid of any preoperative imaging. Considering that a solitary parathyroid adenoma is the most frequent cause of primary hyperparathyroidism (in 80%–85%), bilateral neck exploration is considered overtreatment in most cases. Accurate preoperative localization is required to enable selective minimally invasive video assisted parathyroid surgery (MIVAP) and to reduce the operative failure rate.

Aim of the study: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the diagnostic value of early parathyroid SPECT as compared with planar imaging and color Doppler sonography (CDS) in patients undergoing MIVAP. A total of 15 consecutive patients with primary hyperparathyroidism underwent planar and SPECT parathyroid scintigraphy before MIVAP (dual-phase technique using ^{99m}Tc -methoxyisobutylisonitrile (^{99m}Tc -MIBI) and a double-tracer subtraction technique using a delayed ^{99m}Tc -pertechnetate scan).

Results: The average time for surgery was 35 min (range, 25–40 min). Serum calcium, phosphorus and parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels of patients before surgery was (Ca – 2.87 +/- 0.32 mmol/l, iCa – 1.4 +/- 0.2 mmol/l, P – 0.79 +/- 0.16, PTH – 185 pg/ml (Me)) and 24 h after surgery (Ca – 2.51 +/- 1.2 mmol/l, iCa – 1.1 +/- 1.2 mmol/l, P – 0.82 +/- 0.76, PTH – 100 pg/ml (Me)). All patients had histopathologic examination of the removed glands (single adenoma). SPECT was superior to planar imaging in 2 patients with multinodular goiters, compared with CDS in patients with goiters and ectopic adenoma. Planar parathyroid imaging (80%, 3 false negative findings) and CDS (74%, 4 false negative findings) are less sensitive compared with SPECT (93%, 1 false negative findings).

Conclusion: Preoperative scintigraphic imaging in patients with primary hyperparathyroidism is essential for accurate localization of parathyroid adenomas and for the selection of patients who are candidates for MIVAP.

Key words: Diagnostic Imaging; Preoperative Period; Technetium Tc 99m Sestamibi; Hyperparathyroidism, Primary; Video-Assisted Surgery; Tomography, Emission-Single-Photon; Ultrasonography, Doppler, Color

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Does BMI contribute negative scintigraphic findings in patients with primary hyperparathyroidism?

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Introduction: Localizing studies seem to be the key for determining the optimal surgical strategy in patients with primary hyperparathyroidism (PHPT). Understanding the factors that affect the accuracy of parathyroid localization test ^{99m}Tc -MIBI (MIBI) scanning will allow the surgeon to develop a successful surgical strategy in a given patient. **Aim:** The aim of this study was to identify factors that affect the success of localizing study in patients with PHPT.

Material and methods: The study group included 52 patients with PHPT who underwent MIBI scan and parathyroidectomy at Clinical centre of Vojvodina. The disease is in all cases verified pathohistologically. We analyze variables age, body mass index (BMI), ionizing calcium (Ca), phosphorus (P), serum PTH level, and gland volume (GV) versus the detection rate of individual abnormal glands on MIBI. Nonparametric tests for statistic significance and multiple regression analyses were used.

Results: Of the total of 56 abnormal glands analyzed, 92% involved single adenomas in PHPT and 8% double adenomas in PHPT. Scintigraphic sensitivity was 85%, 100 % specificity with 7 false negative findings. Patients with false negative findings were overweight, but not obese (BMI – 27 +/- 1.5 kg/m²) with lesser GV (median 12.5 cm³ oposite 27.3 cm³ in positive group), significantly lower ionised Ca and higher P. Serum PTH was not different between groups. In patients with negative scintigraphic findings we found negative significant correlation between BMI and GV (r -0.5).

Conclusion: Gland size is the strongest independent predictor of successful localization. Preoperatively, higher Ca levels, lower P in patients with lesser BMI are good indicators about the accuracy of localizing tests.

Key words: Hyperparathyroidism, Primary; Radionuclide Imaging; Technetium Tc 99m Sestamibi; Sensitivity and Specificity; Diagnostic Errors; Body Mass Index